

Complex Formation of Co(II) with N-Benzenesulphonyl-L-Cysteine*

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pH-metric study of the reaction between Co(II) and N-benzene-sulphonyl-L-cysteine $C_6H_5SO_2NHCH(COOH)CH_2SH$ indicated the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 metal:ligand complexes having the co-ordination patterns $[CoNS]$ and $[CoN_2S_2]$ respectively. Complete deprotonation of the -COOH group before the start of complex formation suggested non-involvement of this group in co-ordination. Stepwise formation constants (K_1 and K_2) and the successive acid dissociation constants (k_{2NH} , k_{1NH}) of the 1:2 complex have been evaluated by following the procedure of Irving and Rossotti. Values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$, pK_{2NH} and pK_{1NH} are 6.03 ± 0.03 , 5.60 ± 0.03 , 11.55 ± 0.04 and 13.30 ± 0.04 respectively at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$, in 50% (v/v) water-dioxan medium having ionic strength 0.50M ($NaClO_4$). The pK_{COOH} , pK_{SH} and pK_{NH} values of the ligand have been found to be 4.43 ± 0.02 , 11.05 ± 0.02 and 13.44 ± 0.04 respectively under identical condition.

Enhancement of acidity the imido (-NH-) group in the 1:2 complex indicated the formation of Co-N bonds. The extent of enhancement was, however, small compared to the corresponding Zn(II) compound (found pK_{2NH} , 8.20 and pK_{1NH} , 10.30), as probably Co(II) formed its best bonds with (Thiol) sulphur.

STUDY of the interaction of metal ions of different classes with the ligand N-benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteine $C_6H_5SO_2NHCH(COOH)CH_2SH$, here after NBSC or $(\begin{smallmatrix} HS \\ | \\ HN \end{smallmatrix} > RCOOH)$ or LH_s , having suitably placed hard (-COOH), borderline (-NH-) and soft (-SH) co-ordinating groups may provide valuable information about the specificities of the metal binding sites in proteins which have these types of groupings in their primary structures. The ligand NBSC used all its three donor sites, (-COOH, -NH-, -SH) in complexing borderline metal ions, viz., Zn(II) and Cd(II)^{1a, b} but it used only-NH-and-SH ends in complexing a soft metal ion, Hg(II)^{1c}. With a softer metal ion, Ag(I), the ligand formed a 1:1 metal:ligand complex at very low pH values (2.5-3.0) using only the soft mercapto (-SH) group². In the present work the interaction of Co(II) ion with the ligand NBSC has been followed pH-metrically at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ in 50% (v/v) water-dioxan medium maintaining a constant ionic strength, $\mu = 0.50M$ ($NaClO_4$).

Experimental

The ligand NBSC was prepared and purified by the procedure described earlier^{1a}. All other reagents

were either of A. R. quality or properly purified and their solutions were made in double distilled CO_2 -free water and purified dioxan³.

pH-metric titrations of the following solutions

- (i) 0.01(M) $HClO_4$,
- (ii) 0.01(M) $HClO_4 + 0.01(M)$ NBSC,
- (iii) 0.01(M) $HClO_4 + 0.002(M)$ Co(II),
- (iv) 0.01(M) $HClO_4 + 0.003(M)$ Co(II),
- (v) 0.01(M) $HClO_4 + 0.01(M)$ NBSC + 0.002(M) Co(II),
- (vi) 0.01(M) $HClO_4 + 0.01(M)$ NBSC + 0.003(M) Co(II),

were performed in 50% (v/v) water-dioxan medium with a standard NaOH solution in the same solvent medium while maintaining the ionic strength constant at 0.50(M) using requisite amount of $NaClO_4$.

pH-measurements were made with a Cambridge pH-meter (Portable Type) having a glass electrode of 1-13 pH range and a saturated Calomel electrode connected to the cell by means of an agar-2(M) $NaNO_3$ bridge. The meter was calibrated using standard 0.01(M) $HClO_4$ solution, phthalate buffer and borate buffer solutions with appropriate temperature corrections.

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Titration curves, pH (volume of alkali), were drawn (Fig.1) and the necessary concentration variables were calculated following the procedure of Irving and Rossotti^{4a}.

Fig 1. VOLUME OF ALKALI (ml) →

Results and Discussions

I. Stepwise Acid Dissociation of NBSC :

Consumption of more than two equivalents of alkali per mole of the ligand NBSC in the pH range 2.2 to 12.8 in the titration of solution (iv) indicated three successive steps of its acid dissociation which can be represented by the following equilibria :

k_{COOH} , k_{SH} and k_{NH} are the successive acid dissociation constants. The plot of \bar{n}_{H} (the average number of protons bound to the ligand ion, $\bar{S} > \text{RCOO}^-$) against pH showed that the steps (1), (2) and (3) were independent of one another and, therefore, the constants k_{COOH} , k_{SH} and k_{NH} were evaluated by curve fitting method^{5a} for one step system and also by the method of linear plots. The refined pK_{COOH} , pK_{SH} and pK_{NH} values are stated in Table I.

II. Formation of Co(II) Complexes of NBSC :

The nature of the pH titration curves of solutions (ii), (v) and (vi) Fig. 1 indicated the liberation of one equivalent of acid per mole of the ligand below $pH \approx 6.5$ both in the absence and in the presence of Co(II) ion. Thus the first step acid dissociation (1) of the ligand (i.e. deprotonation of the-COOH group) was not influenced by Co(II) ion. Therefore, the-COOH group was not involved in the interaction of NBSC with Co(II) ion. Analysis of the titration data in the pH range from 6.0 to 9.5 according to the procedure of Irving and Rossotti^{4a} showed that, for the association of each mole of the ligand species to Co(II) ion one equivalent of acid per gm ion of Co(II) was liberated. Free metal ion curves (II) and (III), Fig. 1, showed that the formation of hydroxo complexes were negligible at the early stages of complex formation. Therefore, from a consideration of the pK_{SH} and pK_{NH} values of the ligand (Table 1) and the pH range of the buffer region in the titration of solutions (v) and (vi), stepwise complex formation of Co(II) with the ligand

TABLE I—PROTON-LIGAND AND CO(II)-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF NBSC COMPLEXES AT $30 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$, IN 50% (v/v) WATER-DIOXAN MEDIUM HAVING IONIC STRENGTH 0.5M (NaClO₄)

	Co(II)	Zn(II) ^{1a,b}	Hg(II) ^{1c}	NBSC
$\log K_1$	6.03	8.33	—	$pK_{\text{COOH}} = 4.43 \pm 0.02$
$\log K_2$	± 0.03	7.22	—	$pK_{\text{SH}} = 11.05 \pm 0.02$
$pK_{2\text{NH}}$	5.60	8.20	10.49	$pK_{\text{NH}} = 13.44 \pm 0.04$
	± 0.03			
$pK_{1\text{NH}}$	11.55	10.30	11.55	
	± 0.04			
	13.30			
	± 0.04			

ions, $\begin{matrix} \text{HS} \\ | \\ \text{HN} \end{matrix} \text{RCOO}^-$, was assumed to take place through deprotonation of the thiol (-SH) group according to the equations (4) and (5).

where K_1 and K_2 are the two step-formation constants. The complex formation curve, \bar{n}_{LH} ($p\text{LH}$)

(where LH stands for $\begin{matrix} \text{S} \\ | \\ \text{NH} \end{matrix} \text{RCOO}^-$ ion) indicated

that the steps (4) and (5) were overlapping. The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were, therefore, refined by projection strip method^{5b} and also by the method of linear plots employing suitable forms of the function:

$$\bar{n}_{\text{LH}} = \frac{(K_1[\text{LH}] + 2K_1K_2[\text{LH}]^2)/(1 + K_1[\text{LH}] + K_1K_2[\text{LH}]^2)}{\dots} \quad \dots (6)$$

Refined values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ are stated in Table I.

III. Acid dissociation of the Complex bis-N-benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteinato Co(II) ion.:

$p\text{H}$ metric titration curves of solution (v) and (vi) Fig. 1, indicated further liberation of more than one equivalent of acid per gm ion of Co(II) at $p\text{H}$ values greater than 10.0, i.e., after $\bar{n}_{\text{LH}} = 2$ and this was accounted for by assuming stepwise acid dissociation of the complex ion, according to (7) and (8).

where $k_{2\text{NH}}$ and $k_{1\text{NH}}$ are the successive acid dissociation constants. Average number (\bar{n}_h) of protons

bound to the complex ion $[\text{Co}(\begin{matrix} \text{S} \\ | \\ \text{N} \end{matrix} \text{RCOO})_2]^{4-}$,

were calculated^{4a} assuming all the Co(II) ions in the form of the 1 : 2 metal : ligand complex in the $p\text{H}$ range from 10.0 to 12.8. From the \bar{n}_h ($p\text{H}$) plot it was found that the acid dissociation steps (7) and (8) were overlapping. The refined values of $k_{2\text{NH}}$ and $k_{1\text{NH}}$ were evaluated by the method of linear plot employing suitable forms of the function:

$$\bar{n}_h = \frac{(2[\text{H}^+]^2/k_{2\text{NH}}k_{1\text{NH}} + [\text{H}^+]/k_{1\text{NH}})}{([\text{H}^+]^2/k_{2\text{NH}}k_{1\text{NH}} + [\text{H}^+]/k_{1\text{NH}} + 1)} \quad \dots (9)$$

Refined $pK_{2\text{NH}}$ and $pK_{1\text{NH}}$ values are stated in Table I.

Limits of error^{5c} in the determination of the constants were found out by comparing the experimental curves: \bar{n}_h ($p\text{H}$), \bar{n}_{LH} ($p\text{LH}$) and \bar{n}_h ($p\text{H}$) with the calculated ones obtained from appropriate function using refined values of the constants and experimental values of $p\text{H}$ or $p\text{LH}$ as the case may be. Standard deviations^{4b} were calculated and were found to be $\pm 0.015 \sim \pm 0.020$.

Formation constants of Co(II) complexes are found to be lower than those of the corresponding complexes of Zn(II)^{1a,b} under identical condition. This may be due to more favourable entropy effect arising from tridentate chelation in the case of Zn(II). Enhancement of acidity of the imido (-NH-) group from $pK_{\text{NH}} = 13.44$ (ligand) to $pK_{2\text{NH}} = 11.55$ and $pK_{1\text{NH}} = 13.30$ in the 1 : 2 Co(II) : ligand complex indicates the formation of metal-nitrogen bonds⁶. But as in the case of bis-N-benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteinato Hg(II)^{1c}, the enhancement of imido acidity in the present case was also small compared to that in the corresponding Zn(II) compound^{1a,b}. This may probably be due to the fact that Co(II) being a softer Lewis acid than Zn(II)⁷, forms much stronger bonds with thiol sulphur than those with imido nitrogen because of the ability⁸ of thiol sulphur to form much stronger σ -bonds due to its higher polarisability, together with π -bonds by back receiving of electron density from metal ion $d\pi$ orbitals in to the vacant $d\pi$ orbitals of its own.

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